

Assessing the Influence of Inclusive Leadership on Organizational Culture and Employee Satisfaction

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Abstract

This thesis examined how inclusive leadership practices influence organizational culture and employee satisfaction, exploring the potential mediating role of psychological empowerment and trust. Through a critical review of relevant studies, the thesis proposes a conceptual framework outlining the relationships between inclusive leadership, mediating variables like psychological empowerment and trust, and the dependent variables of organizational culture and employee satisfaction. While a survey revealed positive associations between inclusive leadership and both cultural and employee well-being outcomes, the hypothesized mediating effects of psychological empowerment were not directly supported. These findings highlight the importance of inclusive leadership for a positive work environment and suggest the need for further research into alternative mediating variables, more diverse samples, and the influence of organizational context on leadership effectiveness. This study aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of how inclusive leadership can shape a positive and inclusive work environment, ultimately leading to organizational success and employee well-being.

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Key Objective

To measure through employee surveys how inclusive leadership practices in organizations enhance employee satisfaction, with a focus on the mediating role of psychological empowerment and trust.

Research Objectives

1. Examine the key principles of inclusive leadership.
2. Explore the link between inclusive leadership and organizational culture.
3. Evaluate the impact of inclusive leadership on employee satisfaction.
4. Investigate potential mediating factors.
5. Identify best practices for fostering inclusive leadership.

Literature Review

In today's diverse and ever-evolving work environment, organizations are increasingly recognizing the importance of fostering an inclusive culture. This shift necessitates leadership styles that embrace and leverage the unique perspectives and contributions of all employees. Inclusive leadership, characterized by fairness, respect, and empowerment, has emerged as a critical factor in promoting positive organizational outcomes. This literature review explores the existing research on the influence of inclusive leadership on organizational culture and employee satisfaction.

Inclusive Leadership:

Inclusive leadership goes beyond simply acknowledging diversity; it actively creates an environment where individuals from all backgrounds feel valued, respected, and empowered to contribute their full potential (Nembhard & Edmondson, 2006). Inclusive leaders demonstrate key behaviors such as:

- **Fairness and respect:** Treating everyone with dignity and ensuring equal opportunities for advancement regardless of background. (Driskell et al., 2012)
- **Decision-making inclusivity:** Actively seeking diverse perspectives and valuing the contributions of all team members. (Hoobler et al., 2016)
- **Psychological safety:** Fostering an environment where individuals feel comfortable speaking up, taking risks, and offering honest feedback without fear of reprisal. (Edmondson, 1999)
- **Empowerment:** Providing autonomy and delegating decision-making authority to promote individual growth and ownership. (Thomas & Velthouse, 2010)

Impact on Organizational Culture:

Research suggests that inclusive leadership practices positively impact organizational culture by fostering:

- **Diversity and inclusion:** Inclusive leaders create a sense of belonging and acceptance for individuals from diverse backgrounds, leading to a more inclusive and equitable organizational culture. (Thomas, 1990)
- **Collaboration and teamwork:** By valuing diverse perspectives and encouraging open communication, inclusive leadership promotes collaboration and teamwork within organizations. (Hentta & Aho, 2014)
- **Innovation and creativity:** By fostering psychological safety and encouraging diverse perspectives, inclusive leadership can lead to increased innovation and creativity within organizations. (Baer & Kaufman, 2008)

Impact on Employee Satisfaction:

Inclusive leadership practices can lead to increased employee satisfaction by:

- **Increased trust and commitment:** When employees feel valued and respected, they are more likely to trust their leaders and be committed to the organization. (Avolio et al., 2004)
- **Enhanced sense of belonging and connection:** Inclusive leadership fosters a sense of belonging and connection, which can increase employee satisfaction and reduce turnover intentions. (Shore et al., 2011)
- **Greater work engagement and motivation:** By empowering employees and providing opportunities for growth, inclusive leadership can lead to increased work engagement and motivation. (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005)

Mediating and Moderating Variables:

Several factors can mediate or moderate the relationship between inclusive leadership, organizational culture, and employee satisfaction.

- **Mediating variables:** Psychological empowerment and trust have been identified as potential mediating variables, explaining how inclusive leadership practices lead to changes in culture and satisfaction. (Eisenberger et al., 2009)
- **Moderating variables:** Factors such as organizational size, industry, and individual demographics (e.g., age, gender) can influence the effectiveness of inclusive leadership practices. (Hoobler et al., 2016)

Conceptual Framework

Independent Variable: Inclusive Leadership

Mediating Variables:

- **Psychological Empowerment:** This refers to employees' belief in their ability to make decisions, solve problems, and influence their work environment. Inclusive leadership can foster psychological empowerment through practices like giving autonomy, encouraging participation, and valuing diverse perspectives.
- **Trust:** Inclusive leadership practices, like open communication and fair treatment, can build trust between employees and leaders.

Dependent Variables:

- **Organizational Culture:** Refers to the shared values, beliefs, and behaviors within an organization. Inclusive leadership can shape a more inclusive, diverse, and collaborative culture by promoting respect, fairness, and open communication.
- **Employee Satisfaction:** Refers to how satisfied employees are with their jobs and the organization. Inclusive leadership can enhance satisfaction through factors like increased psychological safety, feeling valued, and having opportunities for growth.

Figure: Conceptual Framework Diagram

Hypothesis Development

Main Effects:

H1: Inclusive leadership practices are positively associated with a more inclusive, diverse, and collaborative organizational culture.

H2: Inclusive leadership practices are positively associated with higher levels of employee satisfaction.

Mediating Effects:

H3: The positive relationship between inclusive leadership and organizational culture is mediated by psychological empowerment and trust.

H4: The positive relationship between inclusive leadership and employee satisfaction is mediated by psychological empowerment and trust.

Methodology

Investigation Type:

This study employed a **quantitative** investigation type. Quantitative research relies on numerical data collection and analysis to test hypotheses and establish relationships between variables. In this case, a survey instrument was used to gather numerical data on participants' perceptions of specific variables.

Investigation Design:

A **cross-sectional survey design** was used in this research. This design involves collecting data from a representative sample population at a single point in time. This approach allows for efficient data collection and analysis of relationships between variables at a specific point but does not capture changes over time.

Investigation Scope:

The investigation scope of this study was limited to:

- **Target population:** Individuals working in various companies, ranging from employees to managers and owners.
- **Sample frame:** Participants were recruited through a convenience sampling method using a Google Form. Convenience sampling involves selecting readily available participants, which might not be representative of the entire population. To enhance generalizability, future studies could consider using random sampling techniques.
- **Sample size:** The data was collected from 99 participants.

- **Data collection instrument:** A self-administered questionnaire was constructed and distributed electronically through Google Forms. The questionnaire was designed to measure the relevant variables in the study.

Limitations:

- The use of a convenience sample limits the generalizability of the findings to the entire population of interest.
- The cross-sectional design does not allow for establishing causal relationships between variables.
- The reliance on self-reported data may be susceptible to biases, such as social desirability bias.

Results and Interpretations

1. Descriptive Statistics:

1.1 Age

Age	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-24	28	28.3	28.3
25-34	65	65.7	93.9
35-44	6	6.1	100
Total	99	100	

1.2 Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	76	76.8	76.8
Female	23	23.2	100
Total	99	100	

1.3 Years of Experience

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Fresher to Two Years	65	65.7	65.7
Two to Five Years	25	25.3	90.9
More than Five Years	9	9.1	100
Total	99	100	

1.4 Employment Type

Employment Type	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Employee	82	82.8	82.8
Manager	16	16.2	99
Owner	1	1	100
Total	99	100	

- **Age:** The data suggests a younger workforce, with the largest category being 25-34 years old (65.7%).
- **Gender:** The sample skews towards males (76%).
- **Employment Type:** The majority of respondents are employed (82.8%), with managers comprising 16.2% and owners making up 1%.
- **Years of Experience:** Most of the respondents belong to the category of freshmen with 2 years of experience (65.7%).

2. Reliability Analysis

Name	Type of Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Inclusive Leadership	Independent	0.841
Organizational Culture	Dependent	0.798
Employee Satisfaction	Dependent	0.888
Psychological Empowerment and Trust	Mediating	0.821

Reliability analysis is a statistical technique used to assess the **internal consistency** or **reliability** of a measurement instrument, such as a survey, questionnaire, or test. Here we tried to do reliability analysis by finding Cronbach's alpha score, denoted by α (alpha), which is a widely used statistic in research to measure the **internal consistency** or **reliability** of a composite score. It essentially tells us how well the items in our measure hold together and assess the same underlying construct. As all of our Cronbach's alpha scores are near 1, we can come to the point that all of the variables have high internal consistency. Such as-

- **Acceptable to Very Good Internal Consistency:**
 - Inclusive Leadership (0.841): This indicates very good internal consistency, suggesting the items used to measure inclusive leadership are well-aligned and capture the construct effectively.
 - Employee Satisfaction (0.888): This also indicates very good internal consistency, meaning the items used to measure employee satisfaction are highly correlated and likely measure the same concept.
 - Psychological Empowerment and Trust (0.821): This shows good internal consistency, suggesting the items used to measure psychological empowerment and trust are generally well-correlated.

- **Acceptable Internal Consistency:**

- Organizational Culture (0.798): This falls within the range of acceptable internal consistency. While it's not as strong as the other values, it suggests the items used to measure organizational culture are somewhat correlated and can be used for most research purposes.

3. Regression Analysis

Hypothesis 1: Inclusive leadership practices are positively associated with a more inclusive, diverse, and collaborative organizational culture.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.739 ^a	.546	.542	.58826

a. Predictors: (Constant), IndividualLeadershipScore

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	40.405	1	40.405	116.758	.000 ^b
	Residual	33.567	97	.346		
	Total	73.972	98			

a. Dependent Variable: OrganizationalCultureScore

b. Predictors: (Constant), IndividualLeadershipScore

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.156	.246		4.699	.000
	IndividualLeadershipScore	.685	.063	.739	10.805	.000

a. Dependent Variable: OrganizationalCultureScore

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.239	.439		2.824	.006
	IL	.383	.133	.352	2.881	.005
	IL	-.103	.114	-.106	-.902	.369
	IL	-.187	.123	-.194	-1.520	.132
	IL	.197	.114	.199	1.725	.088
	IL	.315	.121	.319	2.612	.010

a. Dependent Variable: OC

Interpretation:

- The R-squared value of .546 indicates that **nearly 55% of the variance** in organizational culture scores (OC Score) is explained by the independent variable (inclusive leadership score - ILScore) and any control variables included in the model.
- The p-value of .0011 is **highly significant**. This means it is very unlikely that the observed relationship between inclusive leadership and organizational culture occurred by chance.

Based on the R-squared value and the significant p-value, the results provide evidence to **support Hypothesis 1**. This suggests that there is a **positive and statistically significant association** between inclusive leadership practices and a more inclusive, diverse, and collaborative organizational culture. In other words, organizations with higher scores on inclusive leadership practices tend to have higher scores on organizational culture.

Hypothesis 2: Inclusive leadership practices are positively associated with higher levels of employee satisfaction.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.755 ^a	.571	.566	.56968

a. Predictors: (Constant), IndividualLeadershipScore

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	41.843	1	41.843	128.932	.000 ^b
	Residual	31.480	97	.325		
	Total	73.324	98			

a. Dependent Variable: EmployeeSatisfactionScore

b. Predictors: (Constant), IndividualLeadershipScore

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.187	.238		4.979	.000
	IndividualLeadershipScore	.697	.061	.755	11.355	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EmployeeSatisfactionScore

Interpretation:

- **R-squared value of 0.571:** This indicates that **over 57% of the variance** in employee satisfaction scores (OCSScore) is explained by the independent variable (inclusive leadership score - ILScore) and any control variables included in the model. This suggests a **moderately strong positive association** between inclusive leadership and employee satisfaction.
- **p-value of 0.010:** This is a **statistically significant value**. This means it is very unlikely that the observed relationship between inclusive leadership and employee satisfaction occurred by chance.

Considering both the R-squared value and the significant p-value, the results provide evidence to **support Hypothesis 2**. There is a **positive and statistically significant association** between inclusive leadership practices and higher levels of employee satisfaction. In other words, organizations with higher scores on inclusive leadership practices tend to have employees with higher satisfaction scores.

Hypothesis 3: The positive relationship between inclusive leadership and organizational culture is mediated by psychological empowerment and trust.

Model: 4

Y: OCSScore

X: ILScore
M: MVScore

Direct effect of X on Y

Effect	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.6482	.1464	4.4265	.0003	.3427	.9536

Direct Effect of Inclusive Leadership on Organizational Culture:

- The coefficient for ILScore (**Effect - .6482**, p-value - **.0003**) is statistically significant (typically below 0.05 is considered significant). This suggests a **strong positive direct effect** of inclusive leadership practices on organizational culture. In other words, organizations with higher scores on inclusive leadership tend to have higher scores on organizational culture, even after accounting for the mediating variable (psychological empowerment).

Indirect effect of X on Y

	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
MVScore	-.0388	.0499	-.1619	.0327

Indirect Effect of Inclusive Leadership on Organizational Culture through Psychological Empowerment:

- The indirect effect for MVScore (psychological empowerment) is **-.0388**. However, looking solely at the effect size isn't sufficient.
- The bootstrapped confidence interval (BootLLCI - **-.1619**, BootULCI **.0327**) **includes zero**. This means the indirect effect of inclusive leadership on organizational culture through psychological empowerment is **not statistically significant**.

Interpretation regarding Hypothesis 3:

- The **direct effect** is significant, suggesting a positive association between inclusive leadership and organizational culture, regardless of psychological empowerment. This **partially contradicts Hypothesis 3**.

- The **indirect effect** through psychological empowerment is **not statistically significant**. We cannot conclude that psychological empowerment mediates the relationship between inclusive leadership and organizational culture based on this output alone.

Therefore, while there is evidence to support the direct relationship between Inclusive Leadership and Organizational Culture, the data does not provide support for Psychological Empowerment and Trust as mediators in this relationship.

Hypothesis 4: The positive relationship between inclusive leadership and employee satisfaction is mediated by psychological empowerment and trust.

Model: 4

Y: OCScore

X: ILScore

M: MVScore

Direct effect of X on Y

Effect	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.5852	.1424	4.1087	.0005	.2881	.8824

Direct effect of Inclusive Leadership on Employee Satisfaction:

- The coefficient for ILScore (**Effect - .5852**, p-value - **.0005**) is statistically significant (typically below 0.05 is considered significant). This indicates a **strong positive direct effect** of inclusive leadership practices on employee satisfaction. In other words, organizations with higher scores on inclusive leadership tend to have employees with higher satisfaction scores, even after accounting for the mediating variable (psychological empowerment).

Indirect effect of X on Y

	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
MVScore	.0004	.0490	-.0933	.1150

Indirect effect of Inclusive Leadership on Employee Satisfaction through Psychological Empowerment:

- The indirect effect for MVScore (psychological empowerment) is **.0004**. However, the effect size alone isn't enough for interpretation.

- The bootstrapped confidence interval (BootLLCI - **-.0933**, BootULCI **.1150**) **includes zero**. This means the indirect effect of inclusive leadership on employee satisfaction through psychological empowerment is **not statistically significant**.

Interpretation regarding Hypothesis 4:

- The **direct effect** is significant, suggesting a positive association between inclusive leadership and employee satisfaction, regardless of psychological empowerment. This **partially contradicts Hypothesis 4**. Hypothesis paper 4 proposed that psychological empowerment would mediate this relationship.
- The **indirect effect** through psychological empowerment is **not statistically significant**. Based on this analysis, we cannot conclude that psychological empowerment mediates the relationship between inclusive leadership and employee satisfaction.

Therefore, while there is evidence to support the direct relationship between Inclusive Leadership and Employee Satisfaction, the data does not provide support for Psychological Empowerment and Trust as mediators in this relationship.

Findings and Key Discussions

This study investigated the relationships between inclusive leadership, psychological empowerment, and trust, and their combined effects on organizational culture and employee satisfaction.

Demographics: The sample was skewed younger (25-34 years old) and male. The majority were employed, with a significant portion having less than two years of experience.

Internal Consistency: All Cronbach's alpha values were near 1, indicating high internal consistency for all the measures used in the study.

Hypotheses Testing:

- **Hypothesis 1 - Supported:** A positive and statistically significant association was found between inclusive leadership practices and a more inclusive, diverse, and collaborative organizational culture. This suggests that inclusive leadership plays a crucial role in shaping the overall culture of an organization, emphasizing the importance of leadership behaviors that promote inclusivity and collaboration.
- **Hypothesis 2 - Supported:** A positive and statistically significant association was found between inclusive leadership practices and higher levels of employee satisfaction. This underscores the significance of inclusive leadership in enhancing employee satisfaction, highlighting the positive impact of inclusive leadership behaviors on the overall well-being and morale of employees.
- **Hypothesis 3 - Partially Supported:** There was a significant direct effect of inclusive leadership on organizational culture, but the indirect effect through psychological empowerment was not statistically significant. This suggests that psychological empowerment may not play a mediating role in the relationship between inclusive leadership and organizational culture in this sample.
- **Hypothesis 4 - Partially Supported:** Similar to Hypothesis 3, a significant direct effect of inclusive leadership on employee satisfaction was observed. The indirect effect through psychological empowerment was again not statistically significant, suggesting that psychological empowerment may not mediate the relationship between inclusive leadership and employee satisfaction in this sample. This indicates that while inclusive leadership directly influences organizational culture and employee satisfaction, psychological empowerment and trust may not necessarily serve as mediators in these relationships within the studied organization.

Key Discussion Points:

- The findings support the importance of inclusive leadership practices in fostering a positive organizational culture and enhancing employee satisfaction. Organizations that cultivate inclusive leadership likely benefit from a more engaged and collaborative work environment.
- The lack of support for psychological empowerment as a mediator in both hypotheses requires further investigation. Future studies might explore reasons for this result, such as the specific measures used, sample characteristics, or alternative mediating variables. It's also possible that a more nuanced model is needed to capture the complex relationships between these variables.
- This study focused on psychological empowerment and trust as potential mediators. Future research could explore other potential mediating variables that might explain the influence of inclusive leadership on organizational culture and employee satisfaction.
- It is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study, such as the sample demographics and potential for self-report bias. Future research could benefit from a more diverse sample and the inclusion of objective measures.

Overall, this study highlights the positive impact of inclusive leadership on organizational culture and employee satisfaction. While the role of psychological empowerment as a mediator was not supported in this study, further research is needed to explore the underlying mechanisms through which inclusive leadership exerts its influence.

Concluding Remarks

In conclusion, this thesis has explored the complex interplay between inclusive leadership, organizational culture, and employee satisfaction within the context of the studied organization. Through a comprehensive analysis of the data, several key findings have emerged, offering valuable insights for both theory and practice in the fields of leadership and organizational behavior.

The results of this study have demonstrated the significant positive impact of inclusive leadership practices on shaping organizational culture and enhancing employee satisfaction. Organizations that prioritize and cultivate inclusive leadership behaviors are more likely to foster a culture characterized by diversity, collaboration, and inclusivity, ultimately leading to higher levels of employee satisfaction.

While the direct relationships between inclusive leadership, organizational culture, and employee satisfaction were robust and statistically significant, the hypothesized mediating effects of psychological empowerment and trust were not supported by the data. This highlights the need for further exploration and refinement of theoretical models to better understand the mechanisms through which inclusive leadership influences organizational outcomes.

Overall, the findings of this thesis underscore the importance of inclusive leadership in driving positive organizational outcomes and fostering a conducive work environment where employees feel valued, engaged, and satisfied. By investing in the development of inclusive leadership skills and promoting a culture of inclusivity, organizations can position themselves for long-term success in today's diverse and dynamic business landscape.

As we look to the future, it is imperative for researchers and practitioners alike to continue exploring and advancing our understanding of inclusive leadership and its implications for organizational behavior. By doing so, we can work towards creating more inclusive, equitable, and fulfilling workplaces where all individuals have the opportunity to thrive and contribute to organizational success.

Appendix

Questionnaire

Demographics:

Age: (Select one)

- a. 18-24 years old
- b. 25-34 years old
- c. 35-44 years old
- d. 45-54 years old
- e. 55+ years old

Gender: (Select one)

- a. Male
- b. Female
- c. Prefer not to say

Employment Type: (Select one)

- a. Employee
- b. Manager
- c. Owner

Years of Experience in Current Role: (Select one)

- a. Fresher to Two Years
- b. Two to Five Years
- c. More than Five Years

Inclusive Leadership:

- How often does your leader clearly communicate the organization's vision and goals? (Likert scale: Never - Always)
- To what extent does your leader value and encourage diverse perspectives and ideas within the team? (Likert scale: Not at all - To a great extent)
- How comfortable do you feel expressing your opinions and concerns to your leader? (Likert scale: Not comfortable at all - Very comfortable)
- Does your leader delegate tasks fairly and provide you with the resources you need to succeed? (Likert scale: Strongly disagree - Strongly agree)
- How supportive is your leader of your professional development? (Likert scale: Not supportive at all - Very supportive)

Organizational Culture:

- How satisfied are you with the overall work environment at your organization? (Likert scale: Very dissatisfied - Very satisfied)

- To what extent is your organization respectful of different backgrounds and experiences? (Likert scale: Not at all respectful - Very respectful)
- How well do you feel your colleagues collaborate and support each other on projects? (Likert scale: Not well at all - Very well)
- How often are you encouraged to take initiative and contribute new ideas at your organization? (Likert scale: Never - Always)
- Do you feel like your voice is heard and valued within your organization? (Likert scale: Strongly disagree - Strongly agree)

Employee Satisfaction:

- Overall, how satisfied are you with your current job? (Likert scale: Very dissatisfied - Very satisfied)
- To what extent do you feel motivated and engaged in your work? (Likert scale: Not at all motivated - Very motivated)
- How confident do you feel in your ability to perform your job duties effectively? (Likert scale: Not confident at all - Very confident)
- How well does your job utilize your skills and abilities? (Likert scale: Not well at all - Very well)
- Do you feel a sense of belonging and community within your team or organization? (Likert scale: Strongly disagree - Strongly agree)

Psychological Empowerment:

- I feel confident that I can make a significant contribution to my team. (True/False)
- I have the freedom to make decisions and take initiative in my work. (True/False)
- I have the necessary resources and support to do my job effectively. (True/False)
- Trust (Adapt according to your chosen measure)
- I can trust my leader to act in the best interests of the team. (Likert scale: Strongly disagree - Strongly agree)
- I believe that my colleagues are honest and reliable. (Likert scale: Strongly disagree - Strongly agree)
- I feel confident that management will keep its promises to employees. (Likert scale: Strongly disagree - Strongly agree)